

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION AND BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY: A STUDY OF MSMEs IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

Stella. A. Ogunrinade¹, Prof. A. J. Adegeye², Dr. A. B. Adebuseye³ & A. S. Ogunngboye⁴
^{1, 2, 3, 4} Department of Entrepreneurship, Joseph Ayo Babalola, University, Nigeria

Email: stellabowale@gmail.com¹, aadegeye2000@gmail.com², aaadebusoye@jabu.edu.ng³,
stephenayogboye@gmail.com⁴

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) adoption and business sustainability: A study of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Southwest, Nigeria. The specific objective of the study is to examine the effects of ICT tools on the business sustainability of MSMEs in Southwest, Nigeria. In order to achieve this, survey research design was used to gather data for the study with the use of self-structured questionnaire with 5 - point Likert scale. MSMEs owner who registered with Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) formed the population of 277,270, while the sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. Out of 400 copies of questionnaires distributed to the respondents only 360 copies were validly returned and used for analysis, using a simple random sampling technique. The data collected was analysed with descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 23. The result of F statistics revealed that the totality of the variables of ICT tools have significant effect on MSMEs performance is 97.327, p value 0.000., ICT tools had a significant effect on business sustainability of MSMEs with the values of $t = 4.540$ and $p = 0.000$, The study concludes that ICT use in business operation of MSMEs should be encouraged. The study recommends that the government should make ICT business atmosphere more user friendly by providing ICT infrastructure that will promote the growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in the study area.

INTRODUCTION

Through applying technological tools effectively, users can acquire more knowledge regarding numerous developments in the market, customer preferences, target market, competitors, financial issues that will enhance overall performance of the MSMEs. In many areas, including design, planning, manufacturing and production, research and development, and more, organization can benefit from the utilization of information and communication technology. By incorporating numerous ICT tools into business, we could come up with new productivity apps, backup files, novel marketing strategies, effective social media usage, and much more. The importance of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises in growth and development has become widely recognized (Adanlawo *et al.*, 2021). They are largely regarded as having made major contributions to national development, notably economic development. As a sector, they generate jobs and provide new ideas or items, so contributing to a country's GDP. MSMEs contribute significantly to innovation and growth in both developed and developing countries around the world. They are major source of job creation and employment opportunities (Napitupulu *et al.*, 2018; Niebel, 2018). In Nigeria, approximately 90% of businesses are MSMEs; however, the contributions of these businesses contribute less than 10% of Nigeria's GDP (Adanlawo *et al.*, 2021; Okundaye, Fan, & Dwyer, 2019); this could be due to an inadequate or completely lack of ICT in the operations of MSMEs based in Nigeria. According to Rahayu and Day (2017) and Yunis El-Kassar and Tarhini (2017), ICT acceptance and implementation rates among MSMEs in developing countries such as Nigeria continue to be consistently low. The ICT revolution has helped organizations in both developed and developing countries enhance performance and gain a competitive advantage. (Niebel 2018). MSMEs managers are motivated to embrace ICT considering to the unpredictable global business environment, competitiveness, and the need to enhance business expansion. (Adanlawo *et al.*, 2021; Niebel, 2018; Rahayu and Day, 2017; Yunis *et al.*, 2017). Technology plays a crucial part in the formation of new MSMEs. Technology not only aids in the development of a multifaceted strategy, but also in maximizing the potential of business opportunities. Technology will also help employees communicate more effectively, increasing their work efficiency. ICT has been seen as critical to achieving sales. According to Chege and Wang (2019), information is most likely to have an impact when it is integrated into structured business processes and used through individuals who have the knowledge and training to interpret and apply it correctly. According to Adanlawo *et al.* (2021) and Niebel (2018), the influence of technology extends beyond isolated behavioural changes for optimizing organizational productivity; it also affects the culture prevalent in the organization. However, the use of technology implies a cost: computer equipment and software must be purchased and installed. MSMEs without access to finances may find it difficult to purchase the necessary appliances (Adanlawo *et al.*, 2021; Olowookere *et al.* 2021). The rising cost of production inputs in Nigeria, particularly the cost of electricity and other operating costs, can limit growth, so it is important to investigate the relevance of information and communication technology to the operations of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria in the face of a challenging business environment (Olowookere *et al.*, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are widely acknowledged as critical drivers of economic growth and development, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. MSMEs play a central role in providing employment, generating income, and reducing poverty. According to the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), MSMEs contribute over 49% of Nigeria's GDP and employ about 84% of the workforce (SMEDAN and NBS, 2021).

Despite their strategic relevance, the performance and sustainability of MSMEs in Southwest Nigeria are problematic. Inadequate access to finance, poor infrastructure, inconsistent government policy, and a lack of managerial capacity all contribute to high business failure rates (NESG, 2024). These difficulties are exacerbated by the rapid digital transformation of global markets, which many Nigerian MSMEs are unprepared to deal with. The low adoption of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) among these businesses has been noted as a significant impediment to growth, innovation, and competitiveness (Adeyeye *et al.*, 2023). ICT is widely recognized as a transformative tool for improving business performance. It enables real-time communication, digital marketing, online transactions, supply chain optimization, and efficient customer service (Okwu and Eyisi, 2023). In other emerging economies, ICT adoption has been linked with increased productivity and access to international markets (Adegbite and Olayemi, 2022). However, MSMEs in Southwest, Nigeria have not fully embraced ICT tools due to the aforementioned challenges.

The persistent issues of inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and a lack of technical know-how continue to stifle the growth and competitiveness of MSMEs in Southwest Nigeria. Addressing these challenges is critical for enabling MSMEs to harness the full potential of ICT tools, thus improving their performance and contributing more effectively to the regional and national economies.

Research Question

(i) What are the effects of ICT tools on the business sustainability of MSMEs in Southwest, Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

(i) To examine the effects of ICT tools on the business sustainability of MSMEs performance in Southwest, Nigeria

Research Hypothesis

(i) ICT tools do not significantly affect business sustainability of MSMEs in Southwest, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Information and Communications Technology (ICT)

Information and Communications Technology plays an extremely significant role in helping MSMEs have a hedge over competitors in terms of access to global markets. (Ayandibu, and Houghton, 2017). Kurbonov and Istamova (2021) and Oyelere, Atsa'am, Ayuba, Olawumi, Suhonen, and Joy, (2018) ascertain that the use of ICT in many organizations has assisted in reducing transactional cost, overcome the constraints of distance and have cut across geographic boundaries thereby assisting to improve coordination of activities within organizational boundaries (Azarloo, Eshghiaraghi, Salehi, Habibpoor, and Jahangiri, 2017; Kurbonov and Istamova 2021). Actually, at every step of the process, ICT could help improve the core operations of MSMEs (Gu, Yang, and Huo 2021). MSMEs can gain access to a rapidly flow of information, manage information and resources more effectively, enjoy reduced expenses for transactions, and develop their ability to gather and disseminate information globally by utilizing ICT (Hameed & Naveed, 2019, Gu et al., 2021). ICT adoption in businesses, including MSMEs, has the ability to lower expenses while boosting productivity,

claim Azarloo et al. (2017). Additionally, Johannesson and Jorgensen (2017) contend that because ICTs support efficient organizational productivity and service delivery, they are utilized for client access, communication and cooperation, managerial decision-making, data management, and knowledge management. The claim that information and communication technologies (ICT) enhance corporate performance in terms of productivity, profitability, market value, and share is also supported by Ayandibu and Houghton (2017). Buyers and sellers can use ICT to exchange information and move goods across national borders, expanding access to global supply chains (Gu et al., 2021; Syed, 2018). Rossmiller, Lawrence, Clouse, and Looney (2017) assert that ICT improves business production processes by lowering the need for supervisors through the use of monitoring technology. According to Michailova, Mačiulis, and Tvaronavičienė (2017), there is a significant long-term boost in productivity when ICT is used in organizations. By exploiting their intellectual property online, MSMEs with technology and ideas can stay small and profitable while also generating substantial global sales, according to Sabherwal, Sabherwal, Havakhor, and Steelman (2019). ICT use can help businesses increase outsourcing and lower coordination expenses (Gu et al., 2021). Ayandibu and Houghton (2017) state that the advantages of ICT include more affordable and quicker communications, improved relationships with suppliers and customers, more effective and efficient marketing, the development of new products and services, and easier access to knowledge and training. Prior research identifies the variables influencing MSMEs' use of ICT. For instance, Tob-Ogu, Kumar, and Cullen, (2018) discover that cost, funds, infrastructure, skills and training, management support, and government support attitude are the main factors that affect ICT adoption in Nigeria by MSMEs. The primary obstacles to ICT adoption include infrastructure, purchase costs, lack of funding, management, skills, and government assistance, according to Syed (2018). (2019) Hameed and Naveed. They found both external and internal barriers to MSMEs' use of ICT in underdeveloped countries. Owner manager traits, cost, and return on investment are examples of internal obstacles; infrastructure, social, cultural, political, legal, and regulatory impediments are examples of external barriers. Tob-Ogu *et al.*, (2018) identified several barriers to MSMEs' adoption of ICT in developing countries, including owner/manager characteristics, top management role, firm characteristics, costs and return on investment, inadequate telecommunication infrastructure (e.g., poor internet connectivity, dial-up access, underdeveloped ISPs).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

MSMEs differ from one nation to the next and are generally characterized by their financial strength, assets, or workforce size (OECD, 2018). According to their economic performance and stages of growth, MSMEs are characterized differently in each country (Yeboah, 2017). Sales volume, investment, and employee count are the recognized criteria for identifying MSMEs (Pramono et al., 2021; Yunis, Tarhini, and Kassar, 2018). Nonetheless, the definitions are usually based on the World Bank's definition and are generally comparable (OECD, 2018). It has long been known that micro, small, and medium-sized businesses contribute to economic development and growth (Diehr and Wilhelm, 2017; Pramono et al., 2021). As a result of this greater awareness, the World Bank group has committed to the MSMEs sector as a key component of its strategy to promote employment, economic growth, and the reduction of poverty (Bianchi, Glavas, and Mathews, 2017). It is impossible to overestimate the importance of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. MSMEs have been categorized according to a number of factors, including investment, sales, and employment (Broccardo et al., 2017). Even though each economic field uses different terminology, the fundamental idea is always the same. The "definition of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises varies according to context, author, and countries," claim Diehr and Wilhelm (2017). According to Pramono et al. (2021), MSMEs are not multinational firms, international partnerships, publicly traded companies, or large facilities of any type. To grow into a sizable company unit, they can, nevertheless, rely

on ownership and business structures (Diehr and Wilhelm, 2017). Although it can be argued that owners, friends, and family provide 80% of the funding for MSMEs, there are several company structures that can be used, such as private ownership, limited partnerships, contracts and subcontracts, cooperatives, or associations. Yeboah (2017). MSMEs are seen as a crucial tool for economic growth and development in all fields of economics, whether they are developed or emerging (Pramono et al., 2021).

ICT and Business Sustainability of MSMEs

The ability of a business to endure and expand over an extended period of time while taking economic, social, and environmental factors into account is known as business sustainability. It encompasses actions meant to increase productivity, lessen adverse effects on the environment, and benefit the community (Sinuji et al., 2024). Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises make up a major percentage of the Nigerian economy. Nevertheless, these businesses face a number of issues that could jeopardize their continued survival. (Ebitu *et al.*, 2016). In Nigeria, MSMEs' prospects of surviving as a firm could be greatly improved by information and communication technologies. Through social media and the internet, MSMEs can reach a larger audience than they might with traditional marketing strategies. Olatunji (2015) further emphasized how ICTs may boost the efficiency and production of MSMEs. One issue that many Nigerian small businesses deal with is a shortage of personnel and resources. However, with the correct ICT tools, MSMEs may boost productivity, save expenses, and automate procedures. Furthermore, ICT can assist MSMEs in obtaining funding and enhancing their financial management, according to Khalil et al. (2022). ICT can also assist MSMEs in improving their financial management. By using ICT to increase client numbers, boost efficiency, and make financing easier, businesses may solve many of their challenges. According to earlier perspectives, ICT adoption could improve the long-term viability of Nigeria's micro, small, and medium-sized businesses.

Theoretical Review

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The theory of acceptance model (TAM) is an information systems theory that models how users come to accept and use a technology. TAM has become one of the most widely used and influential theories in the field of information systems and technology adoption. The actual system use is the end-point where people use the technology. Behavioural intention is a factor that leads people to use of technology. The behavioural intention (BI) is influenced by the attitude which is the general impression of the technology. The model suggests that when users are presented with a new technology, a number of factors influence their decision about how and when they will use it, notably: Perceived usefulness (PU): This was defined by Fred Davis as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance". It means whether or not someone perceives that technology to be useful for what they want to do. Perceived ease-of-use (PEOU):- Davis defined this as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort" (Davis 1989). If the technology is easy to use, then the barriers conquered. If it's not easy to use and the interface is complicated, no one has a positive attitude towards it.

Attitude Towards Using (ATU): The user's positive or negative feelings towards using the technology. Actual Use (AU): The actual usage of the technology by the user.

External variables such as social influence are an important factor to determine the attitude. When these things (TAM) are in place, people will have the attitude and intention to use the technology. However, the perception may change depending on age and gender because

everyone is different. Venkatesh and Bala (2008). TAM is criticised for not accounting for the influence and personal control factors on behaviour, including the lack of consideration to other factors such as external influences from the environmental attributes, suppliers, customers and competitors (Manueli *et al.*, 2007; Van Akkeren and Cavaye, 1999). Tam has been criticized for focusing too much on individual user factors and neglecting organizational and environmental factors. Tam has been primarily applied in western contexts and its generalizability to other cultures and contexts has been questioned. TAM has been criticized for being a static model, and there is a need for more dynamic and longitudinal studies to capture the complexities of technology adoption and use.

Empirical Review

To ascertain "The Impact of Digitalization on Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria," Shettima and Sharma (2020) carried out a study. The study gathered primary data from 366 managers and employees of SMEs in Nigeria using a standardized questionnaire. The Chi-square test was used to test the hypotheses, and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The study's conclusions showed that ICT significantly affects the performance of SMEs in Nigeria since it automates processes and products, which raises output and quality. Research conducted by Stalmachova, Roman and Mariana (2022) concluded that digital transformation has brought companies to new roles and functions and led to business sustainability in the long term.

Another study by Igwe, Ebebuwa and Idenedo (2020). explored "The Influence of Technology Adoption and Sales Performance of Manufacturing Small and Medium Enterprises in Port Harcourt." The study used a structured questionnaire to obtain primary data from marketing managers, sales and top managers of 34 manufacturing SMEs in Port Harcourt. The data obtained were descriptively analysed while the hypotheses of the study were tested using simple regression. Consequently, the findings revealed that ICT adoption had a significant positive effect on the sales performance of manufacturing SMEs in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Teryima (2018) conducted a study on importance of computers to human development and behaviour, the role of ICT in the administration of Local Government. He concluded that the major existing issues are lack of technical skills, poor technological know-how, constrained ICT development, lack of computerization, negative attitude of government and so on. As a conclusion, these benefits includes; enhanced operational efficiency, improved performance, improved quality of service delivery resulting to customer satisfaction, increase in market share growth and to a greater extent will result to enhanced sustainable competitive advantage. In the same vain, Adesina and Kabuoh (2024) investigated the effect of capacity building dimensions on the business expansion of SMEs within selected manufacturing firms in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. The population comprised 80,072 registered owner-managers of selected manufacturing micro, small and medium-scale enterprises MSMEs in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample size of 498 was determined using the research advisor's sample size table. A structured and validated questionnaire was used for data collection. The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients of constructs ranged from 0.73 to 0.94. A response rate of 98.4% was recorded. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential (multiple linear regression) statistics. The findings revealed that capacity building dimensions significantly affected the Business expansion of selected manufacturing micro, small, and medium enterprises in Lagos state, Nigeria ($Adj. R^2 = 0.499$; $F(5,484) = 146.923$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that capacity building dimensions influenced Business expansion of selected manufacturing micro, small, and medium enterprises in Lagos state, Nigeria. The study recommended that management should focus on enhancing capacity building dimensions to improve the overall performance. Management should focus on reinforcing capacity

building dimensions to improve profitability. This may involve optimising production processes, cost management, and market-oriented strategies which enhance business expansion and sustainability.

Methodology

This study adopts the descriptive survey research design to gather data for the study with the use of self-structured questionnaire. MSMEs owner who registered with SMEDAN (2021) formed the population of 277,720, while the sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamane formula. In addition, from the 400 copies of questionnaires distributed to the respondents only 360 copies of questionnaires were validly returned and used for analysis, utilizing a simple random sampling technique. A 5 - point Likert scale was developed and validated to collect information from the respondents. This research also made use of both primary and secondary data sources for the purpose of investigating these vital roles ICT can play in the performance of MSMEs. Result of the finding revealed a high reliability index of 0.94 and 0.812. The data collected was analyzed with descriptive statistics such as frequency, simple percentages, means and inferential statistics of Linear multiple regression analysis to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. The analysis was done with the aid of the Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) version 23. The nature of the statistical data gathered informed the choice of statistical tool used.

Results and Discussion

ICT tools on Business Sustainability

Objective 1: To examine the effects of ICT tools on the business sustainability of MSMEs in Southwest, Nigeria

Table 1: Business sustainability

S/N	Business sustainability	SA	A	MA	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	STD
1	The company encourages autonomy and team work to enhance ICT use among staff	88 (24.4)	171 (47.5)	70 (19.4)	16 (4.4)	15 (4.2)	360	3.84	0.984
2	There is appointment of an ICT coordinator who can provide technical support	81 (22.5)	132 (36.7)	86 (23.9)	43 (11.9)	18 (5.0)	360	3.60	1.110
3	The company vision of ICT integration motivates staff to use ICT effectively	86 (23.9)	135 (37.5)	91 (25.3)	36 (10.0)	12 (3.3)	360	3.69	1.047
4	ICT integration has been perceived as an important factor in maintaining competitive advantage	62 (17.2)	144 (40.0)	114 (31.7)	38 (10.6)	2 (0.6)	360	3.63	0.908
5	There is company's support to attend workshops or training programs in order to use ICT effectively	71 (19.7)	118 (32.8)	102 (28.3)	40 (11.1)	29 (8.1)	360	3.445	1.162
6	Financial support is provided for staff to attend conferences and seminars on ICT integration	64 (17.8)	86 (23.9)	111 (30.8)	51 (14.2)	48 (13.3)	360	3.19	1.263

7	The company provides consistent hard wares and software updates	48 (13.3)	111 (30.8)	102 (28.3)	41 (11.4)	58 (16.1)	360	3.14	1.259
8	The use of ICT encourages staff to communicate more with themselves	62 (17.2)	122 (33.9)	140 (38.9)	27 (7.5)	9 (2.5)	360	3.56	0.945
9	The use of ICT help workers to be more creative and innovative	101 (28.1)	122 (33.9)	118 (32.8)	15 (4.2)	4 (1.1)	360	3.84	0.922
10	The use of ICT helps the company to develop business succession plan	87 (24.2)	120 (33.3)	102 (28.3)	34 (9.4)	17 (4.7)	360	3.63	1.092

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 presents the results of the mean and standard deviation computed for the variables of ICT tools and business sustainability in the study area. Looking at the result in the table, it can be seen that 91.3% of the respondents agreed that the company encourages autonomy and team work to enhance ICT use among staff. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.84, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.984 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. Team work enhances better job performance and it is a means of division of labour. Some challenges can be solved and short comings of staff can be covered and work continues. Without team work, many loop holes can hinder effective job delivery of staff.

The Table revealed that 83.1% of the respondents agree that there is appointment of an ICT coordinator who can provide them with technical support. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.60, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.110 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. Time to time scheduling of ICT instructor through training and technical support can help to teach staff in the use of ICT tools. The resultant effect of this will be enhanced performance.

From the table, 86.7% of the respondents agree that the company vision of ICT integration motivates staff to use ICT effectively. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.69, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.047 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. in order to motivate workers most companies try to have a robust ICT programmes for their staff. This has proven to be helpful over the years by beefing up staff knowledge in the use of ICT tools in the study area. Also from the same table, 88.9% of the respondents agree that ICT integration has been perceived as an important factor in maintaining competitive advantage. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.63, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.908 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. The proactive strategies of company management with ICT integration make their products and services to continually be top in the market environment. This help a great deal in maintaining high competitiveness.

However, 80.8% of the respondents agree that there is company's support to attend workshops or training programs in order to use ICT effectively. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.45 was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.162 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. Training and workshop programmes on ICT tolls are essentials for effective performance. It was revealed from the study area by 72.5% of the respondents that financial support is provide for staff to attend conferences and seminars on ICT. This was based on the fact that the mean

value computed for the perception question, 3.19, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.263 that indicated just a slight high dispersion from the mean. Financial support to members of staff on training is a motivation for them to take the training serious and get the best out of it.

The use of hardware and software skill is an integral part of ICT training and use. It is on this note that 72.4% respondents from the study area agree that company provides consistent hardware and software updates. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.14, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.259 that indicated just a slight high dispersion from the mean. From time to time, new versions of software for ICT come out. It is therefore necessary to update the current version of ICT software in use. Without this, the old version of the ICT tools in use may not be able to perform some certain functions.

The use of phone calls in communication is getting reduced due to high charges. Communication through short text messages and emails is now the order of the day. That is why WhatsApp is gaining more attention as one of the tools in ICT use. 90% of the respondents in the study area agree that the use of ICT encourages staff communication more with them. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.59, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.945 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. This result buttresses the earlier result that ICT tools helps in better communication.

From the Table, 94.8% of the respondents agree that the use of ICT tools help workers to be more creative and innovative. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.84, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.922 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. With the current development in artificial intelligence, ICT tools users have answers to virtually all questions and this can make staff to be creative because there is no question that cannot be solved.

The results from Table revealed that 85.8% of the respondents agree that the use of ICT tools helps the company to develop business succession plan. This was based on the fact that the mean value computed for the perception question, 3.63, was greater than the acceptable mean of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.092 that indicated just a slight dispersion from the mean. As part of business sustainability, succession plan is also very important. If not present efforts will be stagnated without a good succession plan.

In conclusion, the respondents in the study area agree that business sustainability impact greatly on performance of micro, small and medium enterprises in the study area. The finding corroborated with the Research conducted by Stalmachova, Roman and Mariana (2022) concluded that digital transformation has brought companies to new roles and functions and led to business sustainability in the long term.

Table 2. Regression results for ICT tools and performance of MSMEs.
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.210	2.403		5.497	.000
	Business Sustainability	.277	.061	.229	4.540	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance
Source: Author's Computation, 2025

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: Business sustainability does not have significant effect on MSMEs performance in Southwest, Nigeria.

The results from Table 2, show that there is positive relationship between business sustainability and performance of MSMEs with the standardized beta value (B = 0.229). The table further shows that business sustainability had a significant effect on MSMEs performance with the values of t = 4.540 and p = 0.000 respectively. This is because the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that business sustainability does not have significant effect on MSMEs performance is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The implication of the result is that a unit change in business sustainability will result to 0.229 unit change in MSMEs performance in the study area. This confirms earlier a finding by Asunka (2016) asserts that Information and communication technologies (ICTs) have the potential to significantly increase MSMEs' chances of surviving in Nigeria. ICTs can help MSMEs expand their customer base.

Conclusion

Information technology has the potential to transform how a corporation runs and competes. Information systems must be considered strategically, and relevant technological expenditures must be made to assist the company in meeting its objectives. The evidence also reveals that use of ICT for increased productivity entirely depends on the tools employed and how efficiently the technologies are being used. Findings from the study reveal clearly that ICT has a major influence in the improvement of productivity and economic activity. Firms generally enter into business to make a profit, and ICT not only helps to increase productivity but also quality, making the way businesses operate less complicated, saving time, and disclosing new business trends and how businesses should respond to such change. The study concludes that Information and Communications Technology positively have impact on the performance of MSMEs operation in Nigeria,

Recommendations

In view of the above conclusion the following recommendations were made:

- i. The government should provide Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises with ICT adoption training and consulting programmes in order to help MSMEs owners and managers to be aware of ICT advantage to business.
- ii. The government should make the ICT business atmosphere more favourable by providing ICT infrastructure that will promote its growth and adoption in MSMEs.
- iii. The ICT industry should come up with awareness to educate upcoming entrepreneurs on ICT value and benefits.

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